

A Case Study on Sri Sri Vidya Mandir School in Jharkhand

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ABSTRACT : His Holiness Sri Sri Ravi Shankar is a well-known spiritual leader and humanitarian whose mission is of uniting the world into a violence-free global family. He has inspired millions the world over. An icon of non-violence, human values and universal brotherhood, he seeks global peace through service and fostering human values. He is a co-founder of the International Association for Human Values. Motivated by His Holiness Sri Sri Ravi Shankar, founder of The Art of Living and encouraged by his personal encounter with the poverty-stricken tribal families, Mr. Brij Chawla and a small team of volunteers started building schools in highly remote and unreachable tribal villages in Jharkhand in 1999. This paper explores the decisive elements of complete education adapted by these schools viz. development of tribal population, holistic education, teaching methodology, livelihood training. The author also provides from there a detailed account of several innovations which is being nurturing there such as group-based learning, enrichment classes, quality control circles, craft and decorations, quality of teachers by which the pupils has inculcated the human values like compassion, co-operation, friendliness, helping nature, belongingness, caring for each other etc.

Keywords : Sri Sri Vidya Mandir School, Tribal Education, Undaunted Challenges, Livelihood Training, Holistic Education

Introduction

According to His Holiness Sri Sri Ravi Shankar, broad-minded education is always accompanied by a warm heart, education is not just information. It is the culturing of our behaviour and attitude. It is our ability to perceive things better. We need to bring in creative ideas.

We should empower village youths, and bring them self-esteem. Sri Sri Ravi Shankar is a modern day sage who is accessible to people to a nearly unlimited degree. He is a noted humanitarian leader and an ambassador for peace, who contributes on a global scale to a better expression of humanity. For this noble cause he has focused his attention on the

reawakening and observance of human values. Without compassion and care for all living beings, without kindness, collaboration, integrity, truthfulness and sincerity, and without the feelings of interconnectedness of all life on earth, something is missing merely from our lives. These human values can be seen as an attitude that expresses itself in corresponding norms and modes of behaviour. They can be found in all traditions, religions, and cultures. Inspired by His Holiness Sri Sri Ravi Shankar, Mr. Brij Chawla and his team have tried to use his vision practically. They have started a project for unreachable Tribal villages in Jharkhand in 1999. Today, Tribal School Project runs 20 schools which endow with free education from kindergarten to high schools to over 3,600 tribal children in India. Tribal education is about seeding long term enrichment of the tribal community, starting with today's young generation. Schooling for tribal children must be warmly focused on equipping them with knowledge and skills for competence progress within their tribal community so as to achieve self-reliance (Kumar, 2012). There is also a unique focus to provide education to tribal girls, which conventionally have been mistreated. As such, the approach is a holistic one, with emphasis on practical wisdom.

Tribal People and Modern 'Development'

The tribal community used to live blissfully in forests, in a world of their own. They farmed, hunted and gathered fruits and firewood from the forest that ensured natural sustainability. When 'developments' bulldozed their habitat, the elusive steadiness was broken forever. Land was taken away for mining and industrial use, forests were lost to sorting, and animals were driven out of their natural dwellings. The tribal people

could not comprehend why God had abruptly altered his mind about the way they should live, leaving them hanging in the balance for survival. Uneducated and illiterate, tribal people found the languages, laws and regulations, economic transaction, and the intact way of conducting life completely unfamiliar and several persons lost their land. So, it seems that the 'developments' introduced or affected upon them are meant to benefit the 'outsiders', at the expense of the indigenous tribal community. Life for them will never go back to the old way. The tribal community desires help to evolve a new balance, to expand a new way of sustainable livelihood, one that plugs into the larger 'outside world' yet not discarding their traditional wisdom. The hope of the tribal community rests with the younger generations, who are mouldable to bridge the modern world of knowledge and technologies, and the ancient wisdom of their traditions. Most of the students in the schools are first generation learners in their families and villages. They are the only hope for tomorrow (AOL Website, 2016).

An Undaunted Challenge in Upliftment of Tribals Through the School Project

Tribal School Project is about educating the tribal children of today to serve as the seeds of progress, and development for the future generations. The focus of Tribal School Project is not simply on academic triumph but a holistic development in the child's moral value, eco-consciousness, community-oriented. It is not just the students, but intact families who are being uplifted. The tribal school teachers provide counselling to the villagers above and beyond running the adult education program since many years. Regular medical assistance is provided

to the villagers by Art of Living doctors who visit these areas at least once in a fortnight to conduct medical camps. Medicines are made freely available for the patients at these camps. Before Art of Living started its tribal school project, malaria was extensive in the area and child mortality rate was too high. Today, the regular supply of medical help by Art of Living volunteers has minimized the death toll. The team remained unfazed in the face of many challenges that came up while setting up the schools. The first and foremost challenge was lack of proper connectivity to these remote tribal areas. Miles away from roads, there was no electricity, and water supply in the area. Lack of infrastructure prevented sufficient and timely medical help from reaching; leading to deaths of tribal's during emergencies. The Art of Living team led by Mr. Chawla toiled hard to get the electricity lines and the roads built to reach these places. They also created clean water sources by installing hand water pumps at every school and digging wells. The rising spread of Naxalism in the surrounding area was also a matter of great concern. Today, due to the good work that has been happening over the past decade in this area, there is no threat from the *naxalites* in running these schools. Initially the parents were unwilling to send their children to school. They preferred to send children to work or engage them in household tasks or babysitting. The volunteers had to persuade the parents of the value of education and make all the arrangements for the kids to attend the schools. These schools run free of charge and provide books, uniforms, school bags, bicycles and transportation, along with lunch and milk to the students (AOL Website, 2016).

Inherent Holistic Education

Education is no longer just about learning tangible and measurable skills. Our past educational paradigms relied on the "average" measurements and standardization. Children were prepared to memorize information and then take placement examinations. A holistic approach motivates children to learn about a subject. It installs *curiosity* and allows children to learn naturally and creatively. It is also attuned to each child's *individual persona* and learning style, in contrast of the current mass educational system. The biggest benefit of a holistic approach isn't just about mental development, but it encompasses *psychological, social* and *emotional growth*. The schools in those remote tribal areas convey education in a holistic manner as envisioned by His Holiness Sri Sri Ravi Shankar. He says every parent would like to have a child whose personality shines wherever the child goes and it is the personality that is appreciated everywhere. This pleasing personality is what the main aim of this education is. This is very much visible when we observe at kids studying at those tribal schools. These schools have spread the messages of universal love, peace and brotherhood throughout the world. According to Sri Sri Ravi Shankar, "The school now we come to the school. The responsibility of the school is to educate a child at the same time, not to vanquish all the virtues that a child is born with. A child is born with virtues and a school should see that it protects their virtues, that innocence, the sense of belongings, love and trust which every child is born with. Often in the educational system, the school only caters as information bureau, but not as a personality building centre. Most schools can produce great computers but only a few good human beings. We have brilliant

students. They have information about the world. Just by one question they can answer all the information that is needed. But are they good human beings? Do they know how to behave well? Are they cultured, civilized, compassionate human beings? This is a question that every school and every teacher should ask.” (Shankar, Sri Sri Ravi, 2015)

Teaching - Learning Manoeuvre

These schools have used Group-based teaching method for the educators. This constructive method of learning has encouraged them so much. This innovative method helps them in imbibing human values such as sharing and helping each other to grow. Each group is assigned a leader to encourage the leadership qualities in the students. Each tribal school has its own garden in the vicinity of the school structure. The garden is maintained by the students themselves. Fruits and vegetables are cultivated using zero budget natural farming. The students learn the value of teamwork and hard work while toiling in these gardens. Physical activities are an integral part of their routine at the school and sports events are regularly organized where students from all the schools get a chance to come together and interact with each other. The culture of the tribes is maintained by encouraging the children to perform dances and dramas in their own traditional language and costumes. Participating in these works the educators foster these values like compassion, co-operation, friendliness, helping nature, belongingness, caring for each other and hence that can be easily transferred to their students. Here the books that students read, the school activities that students participate, the methods of teaching that are being used by teachers, the role of teachers and pupils are expected to play

in the continuance of the rules and regulations of school, the manner in which particular events are celebrated and are chosen to exemplify their significance, the methods of evaluation, promotion, the way teachers are treated, the amount of freedom they enjoy, the kind of people serving on the school and the way administrative staff functions is monitored etc., reflect and symbolize values.

The school atmosphere is surcharged with positive values to imbibe and internalize. Here all teachers are properly oriented to create such environment for children where those values become vibrant. Their role is to put the child on the right path not by imposing but by watching, suggesting, helping. The school has a well-equipped computer lab that provides access to quality educational material with equipped internet facilities. Because of these techniques attendance is very remarkable in the school and teaching-learning progression is no longer limited only to text books. Once in a year, obligatory excursion tours are organized to give the students exposure to the outside world and expand their thinking horizons. Today these kids have started nurturing the ambitions of becoming doctors and teachers to serve their own community. Teachers are recruited from local tribal villages only so that they understand not only the local tribal languages but also the challenging conditions that the tribal children are in. However, the educational qualifications and exposure of local teachers are fairly low. A Teacher's Training Institute was set up at *Hindoljuri* to coordinate the teaching methodology and upgrade the teachers' competency. The tribal pupils are also superior in arts & crafts and their creativity is encouraged by giving them opportunities to make crafts and decorations at the school only. All

the charts, put up inside the school, are either prepared by the teachers of the school or by the students themselves. The classroom walls are totally surrounded by blackboards where the students can draw paintings or alike of their choices. When considering about these paintings, it is quite surprising to be acquainted with that there is no stipulated teacher appointed to teach them these drawings.

Curriculum Contrivances of the Tribal School

Every morning the students arrive joyfully at their respective schools. Those students who reside far away from their school are provided with bicycles to come to the school. Their day at school begins by cleaning the school campus. This imbibes qualities like responsibility and cleanliness in the students. This activity is followed by fetching water from the hand pumps and watering the plants in the garden next to the school building. After this activity students gather for prayers, which consist of Sanskrit chants and patriotic songs. This activity helps to instil sense of pride and moral responsibility towards one's community, culture and country. After the prayer, students calm down in their class rooms to do exercises and meditations under teacher's guidance. According to the school, these breathing practices improve concentration levels and keep students calm and energetic. The students are encouraged to participate in activities such as singing, dancing, and story-telling to boost their confidence. The education is imparted in the national language Hindi and also in English, while preserving their native language *Santali*. Apart from the languages, the children learn modern sciences, history, geography, ecology and other subjects taught in schools all over India.

Nutritious mid day meals with milk are provided to the students. A lot of importance is given to practical learning rather than the rote learning approach. For example, calculating the area of a circle is taught with the help of a board used by the kids to play archery. This makes learning subjects like mathematics an interesting exercise. Ample amount of outdoor activities happen at the school. Thus, the students go back home happy and stress-free at the end of the day.

Special attention is given to the development plan for the students when they grow up. A vocational training centre is set up to allow the students to learn skills that can help them earn their livelihood. The school uniforms are stitched by some of the students and their elders at this centre. The students prepare pretty crafts items that are sold by the volunteers. The team, running the project, believes that the locally trained teachers are more suitable for the schools as compared to teachers brought from urban areas, due to the fact that local teachers better understand the language and culture of the students. Therefore the team periodically organizes teachers' training workshops to generate quality teachers at the local level. The project coordinators are also working on programs to facilitate the students with skills that will help them to earn a living within their native instead of relocating to urban areas in search of employment.

From Vision to Reality

There is an ancient saying that says: "*Swadeshe pujyate raja, vidwan sarvatra pujyate*" which means - A king is honoured in his own country whereas an educationist is honoured everywhere. Indeed, Education is universal. It goes beyond the boundaries of

nation, religion, race, culture, gender and various others identifications. The knowledge of an educationist is universal. Wherever an educationist is born, he does not belong only to that country but becomes a global person, and then he is no educationist at all. We have to cross the boundaries of identities and become global. Today, one of the main problems in the world is identification. Children have given a particular set of ideas and have not been made to open up to new ideas, not open to the rest of the world. With this they grow up thinking only they are correct, only they are right. How do we integrate these values into one's life? First, we need the present scenario. The present scenario has lots of difficulties. Education is not just stuffing our kids with useful information. It is to make them beautiful citizen of the planet. A child, a beautiful flower of this creation is sent to school and by the time he becomes out of college, he has a stern and an aggressive face, a stern look, a dejected outlook towards life. We need to seriously think about it. Should education not make an individual much happier? We need to seriously ponder on it (Shankar, Sri Sri Ravi, 2015).

Conclusion

Knowledge and spiritual awareness should go hand in hand with social and political system. Only then can justice prevail in the society and there be a sense of belongingness with everyone in the world, irrespective of their religious and

cultural background or age group. We need to impart this education – at the levels of schools and colleges. After visiting the tribal schools in Jharkhand, one can truly feel that this vision of the founder is becoming a reality in this nation with the dedicated efforts of the volunteers of the Art of Living with his inspiration. His Holiness Sri Sri Ravi Shankar rightly says, “Teacher can be a living example to their students. Not that teacher should look for students to idealize them. One who is worth idealizing does not care whether others idealize them or not. Everyone needs to see that you not only teach human values but you live them. It is unavoidable sometimes you will be idealized—it is better for children to have a role model, or goal, because then the worshipful quality in them can dawn.” (Goodreads.com)

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